

ABUSIVE SUPERVISION AND EMPLOYEES' WELL-BEING AMONG PARAMEDICS: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF JOB SATISFACTION

Rida Fatima Chohan^{*1}, Dr. Sadia Malik²

^{*1}MS Scholar, Department of Psychology, University of Sargodha

²Associate Professor, Department of Psychology, University of Sargodha

¹ridachohan20@gmail.com, ²drsadiamalik13@gmail.com

¹<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5110-5924>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16751473>

Keywords

Abusive Supervision, Job Satisfaction, Well-being, Paramedics

Article History

Received on 20 May 2025

Accepted on 20 July 2025

Published on 06 August 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Rida Fatima Chohan

Abstract

The current study seeks to investigate the connection between paramedics' well-being and abusive supervision. It was further intended to explore the role of job satisfaction as a mediator. Moreover, to assess the gender differences among paramedics. Considering the hierarchical structure of healthcare organizations and the emotionally taxing aspects of paramedical work, it is essential to grasp these dynamics in culturally specific settings such as Pakistan. The study's base design was correlational. The purposive sampling technique included males ($n = 154$) and females ($n = 146$) with ages ranging from 25 to 50 years. The scales used were the Abusive Supervision Scale, the BBC Well-being Scale, and the Job Satisfaction Scale. The results showed a strong inverse relationship between job satisfaction, employees' physical and mental health, and abusive supervision. The association between abusive supervision and both characteristics was mediated by work satisfaction. In particular, a higher degree of abusive supervision was associated with lower job satisfaction, which led to lower psychological and physical well-being. Additionally, independent t-tests showed that although abusive supervision or job satisfaction show no significant differences between genders but male paramedics showed significantly higher psychological wellbeing ($p = .040$) and overall wellbeing ($p = .016$) than their female employees. The results imply that workplace stressors that affect well-being are influenced by gender-specific experiences and societal expectations. The study demonstrates the negative effects of abusive supervision on paramedics' physical and emotional well-being and identifies job satisfaction as a protective factor against abusive supervision. The results are consistent with the Conservation of Resources (COR) theory, showing that job satisfaction serves as a psychological barrier to prevent resource depletion brought on by poor leadership. These findings, which focus on the need for leadership reform, supervisors' accountability, staff wellbeing initiatives, and gender-inclusive support systems in Pakistani healthcare settings, are important for policymakers and healthcare leaders.

INTRODUCTION

Abusive supervision, which is described as supervisors' persistent, aggressive behavior toward their subordinates, has become a major concern in many corporate contexts, particularly high-stress professions like emergency medical services. Among paramedics, a profession frequently exposed to extreme work pressures, emotional demands, and life-threatening circumstances, this study investigates the psychological and organizational effects of abusive supervision. The healthcare sector of a country has a significant influence on its economy and the nation's overall health (Berry et al., 2010). Paramedics are more prone to experience burnout, stress, and interpersonal conflicts with seniors because they spend a great deal of time on the frontlines of emergencies.

Abusive Supervision, Well-being, and Job Satisfaction

Abusive supervision is a devastating form of leadership that generates various emotional and psychological complications for employees, leading to increasing concern in organizational research over its substantial implications for employee wellbeing within organizations. This form of toxic leadership diminishes the psychological safety and emotional stability of employees, which may lead to stress, decreased job satisfaction, and diminished overall mental health.

It relates abusive supervision to greater psychological problems and stress outcomes such as increased discontent, uncertainty (Ashforth, 1997), serious health complaints, as well as lower self-esteem (Burton & Hoobler, 2006). Here, it is worth noting that subordinates are also concerned with the effects of supervisor behaviors in creating a healthier environment, emphasizing that such behavior significantly increases stress levels for employee welfare. There is, however, evidence that happier employees are more productive than those who are less happy or not happy at all (DiMaria et al., 2020). Abusive supervision, being posited, leads to psychological wellbeing subjective outcomes such as depression (Tepper et al., 2007). It has a significant impact, in reality, on the damage inflicted by supervisors on employees' mental and physical wellbeing (M. J. Martinko et al., 2013; B. J. Tepper et

al., 2017). Toxic supervision, being posited, leads to psychological wellbeing subjective outcomes such as depression (Tepper et al., 2007). It has a significant impact, in reality, on the damage inflicted by supervisors on employees' mental and physical wellbeing (M. J. Martinko et al., 2013; B. J. Tepper et al., 2017). Gilbreath & Benson (2004) have provided a sufficient explanation regarding supervisor attitudes as a significant predictor of employee mental health, and supervisory behavior serves as a gauge for psychological problems. Additionally, they claim that the subordinate does not disregard how supervisor behavior might improve the working environment and that the behavior in question places a great deal of stress on the health of the employees. Employees in a workplace become dissatisfied with psychologically abusive supervisors because of their persistent behavior, even though these are not physical or sexual assaults. From a tension standpoint, the measure of toxic supervision reflects the draining work reactions of employees, worse psychological health, and work dissatisfaction. It can be measured as a social stressor. This explanation draws on extensive historical research (Grandey et al., 2007; Tepper, 2000; Tepper et al., 2004; Yagil, 2006). Tepper claims that over time, leaders' aggressive behavior probably causes stress (Tepper, 2007). There is a correlation between emotional exhaustion, anxiety, and depression in subordinates and abusive supervision (Tepper, 2000; Wu & Hu, 2009).

Leaders' actions frequently result in poor working conditions, which negatively impact workers who are currently preoccupied with their current and future employment circumstances inside the company (Bakker et al., 2014; Huang et al., 2019). This results in health problems and is seen as work-related emotional overload. (Maslach & Jackson, 1981; Xiao et al., 2020). Abusive supervision may indicate that a supervisor is unaware of the dedicated employee's work and how it can significantly harm and emotionally drain them (Kim et al., 2020). Employees avoid even doing work with complete immersion. However, it is a significant source that employees believe they do not care about individual wellbeing; for example, those situations when their leaders are nasty and abusive verbally, they give less effort, are less enthusiastic, and do not completely immerse

themselves in work (Barnes et al., 2015; Huang et al., 2019).

It is a pertinent factor affecting both individual subjective well-being and aggregate productivity at the collective level (Fragher et al., 2005). However, previous studies have shown that happy workers are more productive than those who are less happy or unhappy (DiMaria et al., 2020). Dissatisfied employees generally have a worse perception of well-being and report higher levels of anxiety and despair (Hirschfeld & Rothmann, 2000; Rothmann, 2008). There is a fair amount of data that registers a statistically significant association between the two, the low level of satisfaction being reflected in the diminished well-being of employees who mainly reported increased levels of anxiety and depression (Faragher et al., 2005). Literature suggests a correlation between employee job satisfaction and increased life and family happiness, which in turn leads to a positive impact on general and workplace wellbeing, to some extent (Faragher et al., 2005). Positive correlations exist at opposite ends, such as subjective quality of life and wellbeing are at one extreme, while job satisfaction and job stability are at the other (Park et al., 2018). Judge et al. (2001) have conclusively demonstrated the positive relationships between job satisfaction and wellbeing in the literature. And then it simply means that there is job satisfaction in healthcare services. Research shows that employees whose job satisfaction is low because of abusive supervision are more stressed, depressed, and have a lower level of personal accomplishment (Lian et al., 2012). A mutual outcome that will be disturbed is work satisfaction and general wellbeing, and the adverse emotional reactions triggered by abusive supervision. According to the theory of COR, job satisfaction is a resource that can mitigate depletion of emotional and mental resources consequent to poor supervision (Hobfoll, 1989). Mackey et al. (2017) have revealed a strong negative relationship between abusive supervision and job satisfaction, and its cascading effects on wellbeing and performance.

The Present Research

The focus of this research is to examine the psychological and organizational consequences of abusive supervision among paramedics. It was further

intended to explore the mediating role of job satisfaction. In our study, we considered the psychological and physical aspects of well-being. Studies on these variables are available in other nations; however, in Pakistan, there are insufficient studies on these three variables, particularly regarding paramedics. Moreover, if researchers are present, their scope is limited. This study will provide insight into these four variables and also open new avenues for other researchers to explore the Psychological and Organizational Outcomes of Abusive Supervision among paramedics. That is why I am conducting this study on the Pakistani population.

The current study sample is of paramedics in Pakistan because Paramedics in Pakistan often work under stressful conditions with limited resources, and the added burden of abusive supervision can exacerbate job dissatisfaction, mental health challenges, and poor performance. The current study aims to explore the association between Poor Supervision and mental and physical health among paramedics. Moreover, this will also help in addressing paramedics with any psychological problems by identifying whether the cause of the problem is abusive supervision or something else. Numerous researchers have cautioned that abusive supervision has a substantial impact on both physical and psychological health.

In specific previous research findings, it was reported that healthcare and social services workers are most commonly the targets of both verbal and nonverbal abuse in their working environment (Small C.A. et al., 2006). While they may experience abusive behaviors from several different perpetrators (e.g., patients/clients and their relatives or coworkers), an important supervision that should not be overlooked by those being abused is the source of abuse by supervisors (Withman M.V et al., 2013). However, this animosity causes a great deal of stress for workers, which hurts their performance and general well-being in several areas, including anxiety, sadness, psychosomatic symptoms, and emotional tiredness. (Tepper, 2000). According to Tepper et al. (2017), approximately 10% of employees report experiencing abusive supervision. As paramedics face unique challenges, this study would be of great assistance in developing an understanding of how detrimental supervisory practices are to the health of both individuals and organizations. The study aims to

inform strategies that promote wellbeing and improve workplace dynamics within emergency services by elucidating the ways through which administrative empowerment, job satisfaction, and resilience work. This will ultimately make this study unique because it concerns not only the paramedic organization and peer relationships, but also the broader context of healthcare.

Hypothesis

1. Employees' wellbeing and Abusive Supervision have a significant negative relationship.
2. Job Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Abusive Supervision and employees' psychological well-being
3. Job Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Abusive Supervision and employees' physical well-being
4. Male Paramedics report higher psychological well-being than females.

Figure 1 depicts the connection between Abusive Supervision and well-being. Job Satisfaction is = mediator variable. Abusive Supervision: Independent variable.

Method

Participants

Data was gathered using the purposive sampling technique. Using this method entails choosing representative research participants. A total of 300 paramedics, aged 25 to 50, were included in the sample, comprising 156 males and 144 females. The frequency of males (f=154, 51.4%) and females (f=146, 48.3%) was equal. Furthermore, the sample was categorized based on age, with 25 to 30 years (f=225, 75%) and 31 years and above (f=75, 25%). Further demographics show family systems of nuclear (f=175, 57.9%) and joint (f=125, 41.4%). Further education was categorized as matric (f=117, 38.7%), intermediate (f=114, 37.7%), and graduate (f=69, 22.8%). Moreover, their marital status was such that the frequency of single individuals (f = 190, 63.3%) and married individuals (f = 110, 36.7%) was observed. They were categorized based on their income and experience. The paramedical staff with an income of 10-30k were 152 (50.7%), and those with an income above 31k were 148 (49.3%). The frequency based on experience is as such, paramedics having experience

of 1 to 5 years (f= 213, 71%), and those having above 6 years are (f= 87, 29%)

Measures

Abusive Supervision Scale

In the current study, Mitchell and Ambrose (2007) used the Abusive Supervision Scale to determine how frequently their immediate supervisors used abusive supervision. The scale is a five-item self-report questionnaire. Scores on the 5-point Likert scale range from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree". The Urdu version of the scale was used. The scale has excellent internal consistency (alpha of .93)

BBC Well-being Scale

In the present study, the BBC Wellbeing Scale (Kinderman et al., 2011) was used. It consists of 24 items. Respondents used a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Not at All) to 5 (Extremely). It is designed to measure physical health and wellbeing, psychological wellbeing, and relationships. The items related to psychological well-being were reverse-scored. The scale was translated into Urdu by the

bilingual experts. It has a good internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.935$)

Job Satisfaction Scale

In the present study, the Job Satisfaction Scale (Cook, Hepworth, Wall, and War, 1981) was used. It consists of 7 items. A five-point Likert scale was employed by the respondents with 1 (Completely Satisfied) to 5 (Completely Dissatisfied). It is designed to measure job satisfaction. The scale was translated into Urdu by the bilingual experts. It has a good internal consistency ($\alpha = .80$)

Procedure

Approval from the authorities was obtained. After fulfilling all requirements, the participants were

contacted and provided an overview of the study's objectives. Every subject gave their informed consent and voluntarily took part in the study. They were credited for their participation and coordination in the research.

Result

The current study focused on exploring the impact of abusive supervision on the mental and physical health of paramedics. A variety of statistical techniques were applied to the data. The results of the present study consisted of descriptive, correlation, regression, and t-test analyses. For more advanced analysis, mediation was also executed.

Table 1: Psychometric Properties of the Study Variables (N=300)

Variables	k	M	SD	A	Range	
					Min	Max
AS	5	13.7	4.7	.74	5	25
BBC	24	29	14.27	.89	24	50
JS	7	19.7	4.3	.76	7	35

Note. AS= Abusive Supervision; BBC= BBC Wellbeing Scale; JS =Job Satisfaction

Table 1 presents the means, standard deviations, and reliability of each variable. All variables in the results have strong alpha reliability. The results of the normality analysis indicate that the data were

normally distributed, with skewness values ranging from -1 to +1. Additionally, the results show suitable variability with an actual and potential range that is approximately equal across all scales.

Table 2: Correlation of the Study Variables (N=300)

Variables	1	2	3	4	5
AS	-	-.22**	-.23**	-.19**	-.22**
BBC	-	-	.94**	.84**	.33**
PSYC wellbeing	-	-	-	.75**	.34**
PHYS wellbeing	-	-	-	-	.35**
JS	-	-	-	-	-

Note. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$. AS= Abusive Supervision JS= Job Satisfaction; BBC= BBC Wellbeing Scale, Psys wellbeing= Psychological wellbeing, Phys well-being= Physical wellbeing

To investigate the connections between the study variables, a Pearson correlation analysis was performed. Abusive Supervision was significantly negatively correlated with BBC Wellbeing ($r = -.22$, $p < .01$), Psychological Wellbeing ($r = -.23$, $p < .01$), Physical Wellbeing ($r = -.19$, $p < .01$), and Job Satisfaction ($r = -.22$, $p < .01$), revealing that higher levels of toxic supervision are linked to worse

wellbeing, lower resilience, and reduced job satisfaction.

The Wellbeing and its components were all strongly positively interrelated, with particularly high correlations between the total score and its subscales (e.g., $r = .94$ with Psychological Wellbeing, $r = .84$ with Physical Wellbeing). Lastly, there was a substantial positive correlation between job satisfaction and both

dimensions of wellbeing, and a negative correlation with Abusive Supervision.

Table 3: Mediating role of Job satisfaction between abusive supervision and employees' psychological wellbeing

Paths	Outcome variable	Predictor variable	B	95% CI	
				LL	UL
A	JS	AS	-0.1790***	-0.2937	-0.0642
B	PSYC Wellbeing	JS	0.3305**	0.1406	0.5204
C	PSYC Wellbeing	AS	-0.3451***	-0.5393	-0.1510
D	PSYC Wellbeing	AS(indirect effect via JS)	-0.0592**	-0.1183	-0.0134

Using Hayes's PROCESS macro (Model 4; N = 300), this mediation study investigated whether job satisfaction (JS) mediates the association between psychological wellness and abusive supervision (AS) in a sample of 300 participants. Higher levels of Abusive Supervision were linked to decreased job satisfaction, according to the results, which showed that AS significantly predicted JS ($b = -0.1790$, $SE = 0.0583$, $t = -3.0692$, $p = 0.0023$, 95% CI [-0.2937, -0.0642]). Higher job satisfaction is linked to higher BBC Psychological Wellbeing scores, as evidenced by the

substantial prediction of Psychological Wellbeing by job satisfaction (JS) ($b = 0.3305$, $SE = 0.0965$, $t = 3.4254$, $p = 0.0007$, 95% CI [0.1406, 0.5204]). Higher AS was linked to lower psychological wellbeing, confirming that job satisfaction mediates the relationship between Abusive Supervision and employees' psychological wellbeing. The direct effect of AS on psychological wellbeing was negative ($b = -0.3451$, $SE = 0.0987$, $t = -3.4986$, $p = 0.0005$, 95% CI [-0.5393, -0.1510]).

Figure 2 shows that abusive supervision is negatively related to job satisfaction ($a = -0.17$), whereas job satisfaction has a positive relationship with BBC psychological wellbeing ($b = 0.33$). The indirect effect is ($B = -0.05$), while the total effect is ($c = -0.34$), indicating mediation.

Table 5: Mediating role of Job satisfaction between abusive supervision and employees' physical wellbeing

Paths	Outcome variable	Predictor variable	B	95% CI	
				LL	UL
A	JS	AS	-0.1790***	-0.2937	-0.0642

B	PHY wellbeing	JS	0.1958***	0.0938	0.2977
C	PHY wellbeing	AS	-0.1441**	-0.2483	-0.0399
D	PHY wellbeing	AS (indirect effect via JS)	-0.0350*	-0.0676	-0.0092

In a sample of 300 individuals, mediation analysis was performed using Hayes's PROCESS macro (Model 4; N = 300) to determine whether job satisfaction (JS) mediates the relationship between physical wellbeing and abusive supervision (AS). Higher levels of Abusive Supervision (AS) were linked to lower job satisfaction, according to the results, which demonstrated that AS significantly predicted job satisfaction (JS) ($b = -0.1790$, $SE = 0.0583$, $t = -3.0692$, $p = 0.0023$, 95% CI [-0.2937, -0.0642]). Furthermore, Physical Wellbeing was significantly predicted by work satisfaction (JS) ($b = 0.1958$, $SE = 0.0518$, $t = 3.7793$, $p = 0.0002$, 95% CI [0.0938, 0.2977]), suggesting that greater Physical

Wellbeing scores are linked to better job satisfaction. Higher AS was linked to worse physical wellbeing, as seen by the negative direct effect of abusive supervision (AS) on physical wellbeing ($b = -0.1441$, $SE = 0.0530$, $t = -2.7207$, $p = 0.0069$, 95% CI [-0.2483, -0.0399]).

The study concluded that job satisfaction mediates the association between abusive supervision and physical wellbeing by revealing a significant indirect effect of AS on BBC's physical wellbeing through job satisfaction ($b = -0.0350$, $SE = 0.0151$, 95% CI [-0.0676, -0.0092]).

Figure 3 demonstrates that while job satisfaction has a positive correlation with BBC physical wellbeing ($b = 0.19$), abusive supervision has a negative correlation with job satisfaction ($a = -0.17$). The total effect is ($c = -0.14$), showing mediation, while the indirect effect is ($B = -0.03$).

Table 6: Mean, Standard Deviation, and T-Values of Gender

Variables	Male		Female		T	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
Abusive Supervision	13.14	5.01	13.33	5.25	-.41	.676	-0.037
Job Satisfaction	22.50	5.20	23.57	5.22	-1.78	.726	-0.205
BBC Wellbeing	71.40	15.26	66.91	16.96	2.41	.016	0.285
Psyc Wellbeing subscale	32.92	8.47	30.78	9.39	2.06	.040	0.236
Phys Wellbeing Subscale	20.25	4.63	19.47	4.95	1.42	.156	0.164

Gender differences were investigated using an independent samples t-test. The findings showed no noticeable gender disparities in job satisfaction and abusive supervision, as all p-values were greater than 0.05 and effect sizes (Cohen's d) were negligible. However, significant gender differences emerged in several variables. Males scored significantly higher on BBC Wellbeing ($M = 71.40, SD = 15.26$) than females ($M = 66.91, SD = 16.96$), $t = 2.41, p = .016, d = 0.285$. Similarly, males reported significantly higher Psychological Wellbeing ($M = 32.92, SD = 8.47$) than females ($M = 30.78, SD = 9.39$), $t = 2.06, p = .040, d = 0.236$. These findings suggest that males tend to report slightly better well-being outcomes compared to females, although the differences reflect small to moderate effect sizes.

Discussion

The study explored the complex relationships between abusive supervision and its psychological effects on employees' wellbeing among paramedics, with a specific focus on potential mediating effects. This discussion contextualizes the results within the existing literature, analyzes the study's theoretical ramifications, and makes recommendations for future research and real-world implementations.

Abusive supervision is negatively correlated with two domains of employee wellbeing, encompassing both mental and physical health. Abusive supervision is negatively linked with mental well-being, leading to adverse mental health outcomes for employees. This includes increased stress and anxiety, which can result in destructive behaviors both at work and at home (Shih et al., 2022). Employees under abusive supervision report poorer physical health, which can increase fatigue and other stress-related physical symptoms (Shih et al., 2022). While the adverse effects of poor and toxic supervision are well-documented, some studies suggest that employees may develop coping strategies over time, such as reconciling with supervisors or engaging in positive communication to mitigate these effects (Song, 2022; Zou, 2020). Additionally, organizational interventions, such as training supervisors in positive leadership and stress management programs for employees, can help improve employee wellbeing and reduce the incidence of toxic supervision (Shih et al., 2022).

The present study demonstrated a substantial negative relationship between abusive supervision and the mental and physical well-being of paramedics. According to these results, there is a significant negative correlation between employees' wellbeing and abusive supervision, which corresponds with Hypothesis 1. This relationship has also been documented in the expanding body of international and regional literature. Workers exposed to ongoing verbal attacks, derision, or mockery from their superiors exhibited diminished psychological and physical health. Preceding research aids this, showcasing that unhealthy supervisory behaviors are among the hefty stressors contributing to emotional exhaustion, depression, sleep issues, and even psychosomatic ailments (Tepper et al., 2007; Shih et al., 2023). (Tepper et al., 2007; Shih et al., 2023). Pakistan is home to numerous traditional hierarchical and authoritarian leadership philosophies due to a large power distance (Hofstede, 2001); employees typically do not report or challenge abusive supervisors. These cultural norms, which are pervasive in Pakistan, discourage employees from raising problems, which exacerbates the impact that abuse has on mental health.

In addition to failing complaint resolution procedures and organizational lack of accountability, this cultural silence may cause long-term emotional injury and job disengagement (El-Gazar et al., 2024). Furthermore, the field in which these frontline paramedics work is emotionally and physically taxing. The situation worsens when these people encounter hostile environments from their leaders as a result of their pre-existing elevated stress levels and the lack of psychological support associated with them. According to studies conducted in Pakistan's healthcare industry, abusive supervision raises personnel turnover, burnout, and adverse psychological health (Imran et al., 2019; Iqbal & Rizvi, 2021). These findings raise concerns, particularly in public hospitals where a lack of staff results in heavier workloads and subpar service delivery. The current research further provides evidence that supports that abusive supervision, when not mediated by job satisfaction, negatively impacts individual welfare.

The Conservation of Resources Theory (Hobfoll, 1989) holds that people work to preserve and improve

their resources, such as emotional stability, self-worth, and physical health. These findings are consistent with the theory. These resources are at risk from abusive management, particularly in countries like Pakistan, where support networks are comparatively underdeveloped. This leads to a detrimental loop of mental deterioration that reduces resilience, increases absenteeism, and has a detrimental impact on patient care outcomes. Given their limited presence in leadership roles, diminished decision-making authority, and societal expectations to act by authority, research from Pakistan also suggests that female employees may be especially vulnerable to the emotional effects of supervisory mistreatment (Iqbal & Rizvi, 2021; Farooq & Rasheed, 2017). Existing research shows that the emotional repercussions of abusive supervision may be more severe for women because of fewer coping mechanisms and increased family responsibilities, even though this study did not identify statistically significant gender differences in these experiences.

Finally, the clear connection between abusive supervision and reduced well-being among Pakistani paramedics underlines the immediate essential need for leadership changes, established employee support structures, and culturally aware mental health attributes. Establishing psychologically safe work environments in Pakistan necessitates not only policy changes but also a shift in corporate culture toward one that values accountability, transparency, and respect.

Well-being positively predicted job satisfaction, while toxic supervision remained a substantial negative predictor of well-being, suggesting mediation. Moreover, job satisfaction acts as a mediator between abusive supervision and mental and physical well-being. This supports Hypotheses 2 and 3, confirming that the association between employees' physical and mental health and abusive supervision is mediated by job satisfaction. Enhanced employee wellbeing, better mental health, and more work engagement are strongly associated with Job satisfaction (Wang et al., 2021). Lower levels of stress and better overall health outcomes are reported in Employees with higher job satisfaction (Peltokorpi & Ramaswami, 2021). Improving job satisfaction could mitigate some negative outcomes, as Job satisfaction mediates the harmful effects of abusive supervision on the mental

health of employees (Peltokorpi & Ramaswami, 2021).

Based on the Theory of Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory (Hobfoll, 1989), job satisfaction serves as a psychological resource that prevents depletion triggered by work-related stresses, such as abusive supervision. These findings correspond with this theory. However, according to Hofstede (2001), hierarchical structures, power distance, and authoritarian leadership styles always significantly impede these functional resources. In particular, public health care workers are more likely to put up with abuse because they are aware that they encounter job insecurity, fear of retribution, or a lack of channels for grievances (Ali & Zhuang, 2020).

Numerous regional research studies have been developed to verify the claims of toxic supervision, which is a prevalent top stressor in Pakistan and further contributes to adverse conditions like burnout, low morale, and emotional exhaustion (Abideen, 2022; El-Gazar et al., 2024). In collectivist cultures like Pakistan's, where authority is respected and frequently unquestioned, the effects of abusive monitoring are exacerbated. This happens because, rather than questioning their superiors, subordinates are culturally educated to deal with stress (Zhang et al., 2019; Han et al., 2013). This corroborates a study that discovered a strong link between harmful supervision and worse physical and mental health, as well as less job satisfaction.

Additionally, Pakistani organizational culture frequently lacks institutional HR practices and psychological support for frontline workers, such as paramedics (Aslam et al., 2016). Consequently, these employees frequently lament their workload, erratic expectations, and lack of feedback systems, all of which worsen the harmful effects of abusive supervision. In this instance, job satisfaction is a significant internal resource that fosters well-being and strengthens emotional resilience in the face of organizational dysfunction.

Job satisfaction mediates the relationship between abusive supervision and psychological and physical wellbeing, which is consistent with previous Pakistani research relating job satisfaction to worker performance. (Imran et al., 2019). Farooq et al. (2017) assert that contented workers are more likely to be engaged at work, have improved emotional stability,

and lower absenteeism even when they are not adequately supervised. In light of this trend, it appears that any attempt focused on enhancing workers' job satisfaction, for example, by improving communication, acknowledgment, support, and autonomy, can to a considerable extent mitigate the psychological toll that abusive leadership takes.

Above all, it is important to interpret Pakistan's gendered work environment. Although the present investigation found no evidence of gender differences in supervision, research indicates that social norms, a lack of empowerment, and a significantly lower representation in positions of decision-making may put Pakistani women healthcare professionals at higher risk of encountering covert forms of emotional abuse (Iqbal & Rizvi, 2021). The finding shows that males report higher psychological well-being, thus supporting our Hypothesis 4. Future studies should investigate the interplay between power, gender, and psychological safety.

Limitations and Suggestions

The first limitation is regarding the generalizability. The data is collected solely from the Punjab Province due to time and resource limitations. We cannot generalize it to all of Pakistan. It is suggested that to increase the generalizability of the study, data collection should also be done from other provinces of Pakistan. The causality of the dependent variables cannot be ensured because the study was a survey. Therefore, academics in the future should not rely solely on survey research. The research's cross-sectional design limits the capacity to infer causal relationships. While abusive supervision significantly predicted lower job satisfaction, resilience, and wellbeing, the direction of these relationships cannot be confirmed. To prove causation and comprehend whether these impacts evolve, more experimental or longitudinal research is required.

The study only used self-report questionnaires, which are susceptible to basic technique biases, including response and social desirability. This may have influenced the strength of observed relationships. Future research should consider multi-method approaches, such as supervisor ratings, peer assessments, or objective performance data, to validate and enrich these findings.

Implication

These research findings have important applications for examining how toxic supervision affects Pakistan's paramedic workforce. This research opens up a door for emerging researchers to explore the phenomenon of this type of supervision from a Pakistani context, comparing it to other cultures. Mental health practitioners, health administrators, and organizational psychologists should understand that abusive supervision has a detrimental effect on the mental health of paramedics and causes stress, burnout, and demotivation. Because job satisfaction mediates this relationship, attempts to improve job satisfaction via appropriate treatment, supportive leadership, and recognition will help lessen psychological adverse effects. It supplies a foundation for exploring how employees cope with toxic supervision while working under challenging psychological and physical conditions. Given Pakistan's solid cultural norms surrounding authority and hierarchy, further research may be justified to examine cultural distinctions based on ethnicity and history.

This study further stimulates additional studies into preservative psychological traits, including resilience, emotional control, and associate support, that may reduce the harmful impacts of poor supervision on subjective well-being. Young researchers could proceed with this research by analyzing how various formal and informal coping mechanisms or support networks may ease feelings of emotional tiredness. Future studies can examine how years of service, gender, and age interact to modify the psychological effects of paramedics' emotional burden.

Conclusion

The current investigation explored the effects of toxic supervision on paramedics' physical and mental health in Pakistan, particularly highlighting the mediating impact of work satisfaction and gender-related differences in wellbeing. The results indicated that toxic supervision has a detrimental impact on both mental and physical health and is notably linked to decreased job satisfaction. Mediation analysis demonstrated the role of job satisfaction as a mediator between abusive supervision and both psychological and physical well-being, aligned with the theory of Conservation of Resources (COR) theory.

Furthermore, the gender-based research revealed that although work satisfaction and abusive supervision were comparable for male and female paramedics, male paramedics experienced much higher psychological wellness than their female counterparts. These differences demonstrate how gender-specific coping strategies and experiences in medical settings can affect psychological outcomes, particularly in culturally hierarchical contexts such as Pakistan.

These findings highlight how important it is for healthcare institutions to support respectful leadership, have psychologically safe workplaces, and create gender-sensitive strategies. The sustainability of emergency medical care in Pakistan relies on enhancing employee wellbeing while minimizing the devastating effects of toxic supervision. This can be achieved by boosting job fulfillment through organizational support and equitable monitoring.

REFERENCES

- Ashforth, B. (1994). Petty Tyranny in Organizations. *Human relations*, 47(7), 755-778. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00187267940470070>
- Ashforth, B. E. (1997). Petty tyranny in organizations: A preliminary examination of antecedents and consequences. *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences/Revue Canadienne des Sciences de l'Administration*, 14(2), 126-140. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1936-4490.1997.tb00124.x>
- Burton, J. P., & Hoobler, J. M. (2006). Subordinate self-esteem and abusive supervision. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 18(3), 340-355. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40604544>
- DiMaria, C. H., Peroni, C., & Sarracino, F. (2020). Happiness Matters: Productivity Gains from Subjective Well-being. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 21(1), 139-160. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-019-00074-1>
- Faragher, E. B., Cass, M., & Cooper, C. L. (2005). The relationship between job satisfaction and health: a meta-analysis. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 62(2), 105-112. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oem.2002.006734>
- Farooq, R., & Rasheed, H. (2017). Organizational Justice and Job Performance in Pakistani Organizations: A Study in the *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences*.
- Harris, L. C., & Ogbonna, E. (2011). Antecedents and consequences of management-espoused organizational cultural control. *Journal of Business Research*, 64(5), 437-445. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2010.03.002>
- Hobfoll, S. E. (1989). Conservation of resources: A new attempt at conceptualizing stress. *American psychologist*, 44(3), 513.
- Imran, R., Majeed, M., & Ayub, A. (2019). Impact of toxic leadership on job burnout and turnover intentions: Mediating role of job satisfaction. *Abasyn Journal of Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOTB-12-2022-0237>
- Iqbal, N., & Rizvi, T. (2021). Workplace bullying and stress in Pakistani hospitals: A gendered analysis. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*.
- Judge, T. A., Thoresen, C. J., Bono, J. E., & Patton, G. K. (2001). The job satisfaction-job performance relationship: A qualitative and quantitative review. *Psychological bulletin*, 127(3), 376. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.127.3.376>
- Kinderman, P., Schwannauer, M., Pontin, E., & Tai, S. (2011). The development and validation of a general measure of wellbeing: the BBC Well-being Scale. *Quality of Life Research*, 20, 1035-1042.
- Li, Y., Wang, Z., Yang, L. Q., & Liu, S. (2016). The crossover of psychological distress from leaders to subordinates in teams: The role of abusive supervision, psychological capital, and team performance. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 21(2), 142. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0039960>

- Mackey, J. D., Frieder, R. E., Brees, J. R., & Martinko, M. J. (2017). Abusive supervision: A meta-analysis and empirical review. *Journal of Management*, 43(6), 1940-1965. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01492063155739>
- Mitchell, M. S., & Ambrose, M. L. (2007). Abusive supervision and workplace deviance and the moderating effects of negative reciprocity beliefs. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92(4), 1159. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.92.4.1159>
- Pan, F. C. (2015). Practical application of importance-performance analysis in determining critical job satisfaction factors of a tourist hotel. *Tourism Management*, 46, 84-91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2014.06.004>
- Peltokorpi, V., & Ramaswami, A. (2021). Abusive supervision and subordinates' physical and mental health: The effects of job satisfaction and power distance orientation. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 32(4), 893-919. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2018.1511617>
- Peltokorpi, V., & Ramaswami, A. (2021). Abusive supervision and subordinates' physical and mental health: The effects of job satisfaction and power distance orientation. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 32(4), 893-919. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2018.1511617>
- Rothmann, S. (2008). Job satisfaction, occupational stress, burnout, and work engagement as components of work-related wellbeing. *SA journal of industrial psychology*, 34(3), 11-16.
- Shih, F. C., Yeh, S. C. J., & Hsu, W. L. (2023). Abusive supervision and employee wellbeing of nursing staff: The mediating role of occupational stress. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 79(2), 664-675. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.15538>
- Shih, F. C., Yeh, S. C. J., & Hsu, W. L. (2023). Abusive supervision and employee wellbeing of nursing staff. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.15538>
- Tepper, B. J. (2000). Consequences of abusive supervision. *Academy of Management Journal*, 43(2), 178-190. <https://doi.org/10.5465/1556375>
- Tepper, B. J., Simon, L., & Park, H. M. (2007). Abusive supervision. *Journal of Management*, 33(3), 261-289. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190224851.013.105>
- Tepper, B. J., Simon, L., & Park, H. M. (2017). Abusive supervision. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 4(1), 123-152. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-041015-062539>
- Tu, M., Bono, J. E., Shum, C., & LaMontagne, L. (2018). Breaking the Cycle: The Effects of Role Model Performance and Ideal Leadership Self-Concepts on Abusive Supervision Spillover. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 103(7), 689-702. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0000297>
- Wang, I. A., Lin, S. Y., Chen, Y. S., & Wu, S. T. (2022). The influences of abusive supervision on job satisfaction and mental health: the path through emotional labor. *Personnel Review*, 51(2), 823-838. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-11-2018-0465>
- Whitman, M. V., Halbesleben, J. R., & Holmes IV, O. (2014). Abusive supervision and feedback avoidance: The mediating role of emotional exhaustion. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.1852>
- Zou, W. (2020). A Review of the Impact and Coping Methods of Abusive Supervision on Employees. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 8(2), 713-725. <http://doi.org/10.4236/ojbm.2020.82043>